

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable 2.4 Genome Detective Platform adaptations for plant viruses

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Genome Detective Platform adaptations for plant viruses

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ONT: Oxford Nanopore Technologies

RCA: Rolling circle amplification

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Within the Virtigation project, dedicated to combating viral diseases in tomato and cucurbits, Genome Detective Platform is being used as a web-based software application to assemble the genomes of viruses quickly and accurately from next generation sequencing data. Two important changes were made to the Genome Detective Platform to accommodate the collection and analysis of plant virus samples, including metagenomic viral sequences and epidemiological metadata annotations, for the analysis of plant virus outbreaks. Firstly, it is now possible to store, manage, import, export and explore metadata based on the descriptor list created in Deliverable 2.1. The metadata is linked to a sample, and can be entered via a web interface, or via Excel upload. Secondly, the bio-informatics analysis for full-length viral nanopore sequencing (ONT) Rolling Circle Amplification wet lab protocol developed in T2.2 is supported in the analysis pipelines.

INTRODUCTION

The VIRTIGATION project is aimed at understanding the plant-virus-vector interactions, specifically the factors that drive the emergence and spread of (new) virus variants. In terms of the WP2 ('Develop tools and methods to sequence full viral genomes and web interface for monitoring virus diversity and factors conducive to outbreaks'), such factors include biological properties (i.e. possible resistances) of the host, environmental and cropping conditions, vector data (if relevant), co-infections with other pathogens, and other relevant data. These data can now be linked with extensive analysis of virus isolates by deep sequencing. Here, we present the deliverable 2.4 that contains the adaptations that were made to Genome Detective Platform to enable the linking of descriptors (epidemiological metadata) to samples, and the analysis of full-length genomic data sequenced using Rolling Circle Amplification.

ADDING DESCRIPTORS TO A SAMPLE

This section describes how users can link descriptors relevant for epidemiological monitoring to their samples. These descriptors were created in T2.1, and by supporting them in Genome Detective Platform, they can be stored, managed and analysed together with viral sequence data. This functionality is available to Virtigation consortium users since release 2.14.0, which was released on 22/04/2024. Linking descriptors to samples can be done in two different ways: via the user interface, or via Excel upload.

4.1. Uploading descriptors via the user interface

As soon as a sample has been added to the Virtigation collection, the user in charge will have access to the panels containing Geolocation and Virtigation descriptors, as shown in Figure 1.

SAMPLE DETAILS

GENERAL DETAILS

Sample Id	<input type="text" value="my_first_virtigation_sample"/>
Sample Date	<input type="text"/>

EPIDATA

- ▶ General Epidata Details
- ▶ GeoLocation
- ▶ Virtigation descriptors

COLLECTIONS

Virtigation_Emweb

Figure 1. The GeoLocation and Virtigation descriptors panel are available for every sample added to the Virtigation collection.

There are two ways to add GeoLocation: either text-based, or coordinated based, as illustrated in Figure 2. Text-based entries are converted to geographic location and are stored in a structured way to support further analysis.

EPIDATA

General Epidata Details

GeoLocation

Text-based location

Accuracy

Latitude

Longitude

Google GeoCode

SAVE

Virtigation descriptors

Figure 2: Geolocation can be added either text-based or coordinate-based, here the text-based option is shown.

An extract of the Virtigation descriptors panel is shown in Figure 3. Some of the descriptors are free text, e.g., 'Means of introduction', whereas others are a checkbox, e.g., 'Reason for sampling: symptoms' or a dropdown menu, e.g., 'Type of agriculture'. Some descriptors are auto-filled based, e.g., 'Timing of the first symptoms' if computed based on 'Planting date of crop' and 'Date of first observation of symptoms'.

Virtigation descriptors

Reason for sampling: symptoms Was the sample taken because symptoms were observed?

Reason for sampling: survey Was the sample taken on an intentional investigation or a random check?

Scientific name of the plant or vector sampled If substrate is plant or plant part or a vector specify the scientific name from which the specimen was isolated.

Date of first observation of symptoms Indicate at least year, preferably also date

Sampling/isolation date Date of sampling. At least year, preferably also date

Planting date of crop Date (preferably day-month-year)

Timing of first symptoms When were first symptoms discovered in relation to days post planting. In days.

Identification method Test (method x matrix x target organism) used for first identification including morphological and morphometrical methods

First find or observation? Was this a first find of this virus?

Means of introduction How do you think the virus was introduced?

Figure 3: The Virtigation descriptors, more descriptors are available by scrolling down.

It is always possible to save the descriptors, even if not all of them are filled out.

4.2. Uploading descriptors via Excel upload

A second way of adding descriptors is by uploading an Excel file. For large batch uploads, this method has the benefit that data can be copied over from other systems and can be efficiently imported in the platform. Every consortium member can download the template file for the descriptors from Genome Detective Platform. This file contains two sheets, a first sheet with instructions (shown in Figure 4), and a second sheet where descriptors can be added, the latter named 'Submissions'. The instructions sheet will specify the description and expected value type for each descriptor. The submission sheet contains a column sample name, and sample date; columns for each of the Geolocation field; and a column for each descriptor. The user then fills out one row per sample, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Field Name	Description	Data Type	Mandatory
Sample Name	The name you want your sample to be given in Genome Detective Platform.	Free text	Yes
Sample Date	When was this sample taken?	yyyy-mm-dd	Yes
Text-based location	The geolocation information can be provided in one of two ways. In this field, you can provide the location as "country, city", or "country, city, street address". Alternatively, leave this field blank and provide an accuracy, latitude and longitude in the other geolocation fields.	Free text	No
Accuracy	Leave blank if Text-based location is filled out. Otherwise, how accurately are the provided latitude and longitude to be interpreted?	Possible values: 'Country', 'Address', 'Street', 'SubRegion', 'Region', 'City', 'ZIP'. Only one value allowed.	No
Latitude	Leave blank if Text-based location is used. The first component of any given geographic coordinate. This is the measurement of distance north or south of the Equator, measured as an angle that ranges from -90° at the south pole to 90° at the north pole, with 0° at the Equator. Please provide the latitude as a fractional number, and not in degrees, minutes, seconds.	Fractional number between -90.0 and 90.0	No
Longitude	Leave blank if Text-based location is used. The second component of any given geographic coordinate. This is the measurement east or west of the prime meridian, measured as an angle that ranges from -180° (= 180°W) to 180° (= 180°E). At the prime meridian the longitude is 0°. Please provide the longitude as a fractional number, and not in degrees, minutes, seconds.	Fractional number between -180.0 and 180.0	No
Reason for sampling: symptoms	Was the sample taken because symptoms were observed?	Yes/No	Yes
Reason for sampling: survey	Was the sample taken on an intentional investigation or a random check?	Possible values: intentional investigation, random check. Only one value allowed.	Yes
Scientific name of the plant or vector sampled	If substrate is plant or plant part or a vector specify the scientific name from which the specimen was isolated.	Free text	Yes
Date of first observation of symptoms	Indicate at least year, preferably also date	yyyy-mm-dd	Yes
Sampling/isolation date	Date of sampling. At least year, preferably also date	yyyy-mm-dd	Yes
Planting date of crop	Date (preferably day-month-year)	yyyy-mm-dd	Yes
Identification method	Test (method x matrix x target organism) used for first identification including morphological and morphometrical methods	Free text	Yes
First find or observation?	Was this a first find of this virus?	Yes/No	Yes
Means of introduction	How do you think the virus was introduced?	Free text	Yes
Additional information on sampling location	Sampling location refers to where the sample was taken. In this field, indicate any other information regarding sampling location. In particular, indicate whether the sampling was done at a point of entry or during surveillance.	Free text	No
Country of origin for imported consignments/organism	Location from where the organism/consignment was imported (not the same as sampling location).	Free text	No
Sampling cluster ID	Were multiple samples taken in one location? If multiple samples were taken in one location, indicate the number of	Yes/No	No

Figure 4: The instructions sheet of the descriptors template

Sample Name	Sample Date	Text-based locat	Accur	Latit	Longit	Reason for sampling: symptoms	Reason for sampling: survey	Scientific name of the plant or vector sampled	Date of first observation of symptoms	Sa
my_first_virtigation_sample	2022-04-15	Madrid, Spain				Yes	intentional investigation	Solanum lycopersicum	2023-02	
my_second_virtigation_sample	2022-04-15	Brussels, Belgium				Yes	random check	Solanum lycopersicum	2023-04	
my_third_virtigation_sample	2022-04-15	Paris, France				No	random check	Solanum lycopersicum	2023-03-15	

Figure 5: The submissions sheet of the descriptors template. Here descriptors are being provided for an example with three different samples.

Once the user has uploaded his Excel file, a pop-up window will be shown summarising how many descriptors will be added to existing samples, and how many new samples will be created. Moreover, if the user has made any mistakes in his submission, he can download the annotated uploaded Excel file that will highlight the problematic fields in the Excel file. This pop-up window is shown in Figure 6, and an example of an annotated Excel file is shown in Figure 7. This offers an efficient and user-friendly way for a user to correct errors and further add missing data.

UPLOAD VIRTIGATION_EMWEB EPIDATA

- 2 samples don't exist yet, they will be created and added to collection Virtigation_Emweb.
- 1 samples were found in collection Virtigation_Emweb, their descriptors will be updated.
- 0 samples were found, but don't belong to collection Virtigation_Emweb, they will be added to collection Virtigation_Emweb and their descriptors will be updated.

3 samples contain warnings. Warning are indicated in [this annotated file](#). Do you wish to continue the import?

Figure 6: After uploading an Excel file with descriptors, a summary will be given of any samples that will be newly created. In this case the user also made some mistakes in his submission, and he can download an annotated Excel file containing all the warnings.

H	I	J	K	L	M	N
criptors	Virtigation descriptors	Virtigation descriptors	Virtigation descriptors	Virtigation descriptors	Virtigation descriptors	Virtigation descriptors
ampling: survey	Scientific name of th	Warning: missing mandatory value in row 4 column M: Identification method.			Identification method	First find or observation?
estigation	Solanum lycopersicu					
:	Solanum lycopersicu					
:	Solanum lycopersicum	2023-03-15	2023-04-15			

Figure 7: The annotated Excel file containing warnings

The user can then choose whether to correct the submission, or to continue with the upload ignoring the warnings.

4.3. Searching on descriptors

Once a user has added descriptors to his samples, samples are searchable based on descriptor values. A simple example of this is shown in Figure 8, however it is also possible to search on combinations of descriptor values. In the results section of the search interface, the user can select or deselect any of the samples that were found, and can then download an Excel file that contains the descriptors for all the selected samples, as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 8: Using the search interface to find any sample whose 'Scientific name of the plant or vector sampled' contains "solanum".

RESULTS

3 samples found

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Sample Id	Sample Date	Most Abundant ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	my_third_virtigation_...	2022-04-14 22:00:00...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	my_second_virtigati...	2022-04-14 22:00:00...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	my_first_virtigation_...		Influenza B virus

DOWNLOAD QUERY RESULTS (.XLS)

DOWNLOAD ANALYSIS INFO (.XLS)

DOWNLOAD EPIDATA (.XLS)

ADD TO COLLECTION

DOWNLOAD SEQUENCES (.FASTA)

Select one or multiple strains using ctrl + mouseclick

All sequences
 Avian sarcoma virus CT10
 Baboon endogenous virus strain M7
 Bovine retrovirus CH15
 Human endogenous retrovirus K113
 Human endogenous retrovirus K113

COMPARE SAMPLES

Figure 9: In the results section of the search interface, the user can download an excel file containing all the descriptors for the selected samples.

ROLLING CIRCLE AMPLIFICATION PROTOCOL

In this project a novel bioinformatics pipeline was developed to detect and list multiple variants of a viral species within a single sample. This complements the analysis of the data generated with the new RCA wet-lab protocol developed in T2.2.

The RCA protocol copies a single circular DNA molecule multiple times in a linear DNA strand, allowing to sequence multiple copies of a single viral genome in one single read using the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) sequencing platform.

Two mechanisms were combined to improve the quality of the reads to a level where it is possible to detect multiple variants of the same virus species. The first mechanism is adding a pre-processing step to correct within-read errors (RCA preprocessing); the second step is a sequencing-error correction step using information across reads.

The new pipeline is integrated into the web-based bio-informatics platform Genome Detective [1] to make it easily accessible to the community.

5.1. RCA preprocessing in Genome Detective

The RCA protocol generates one large read containing repeated copies of one viral genome.

The software deconcatenates the duplicated sequences and verifies the bases called on each position within the different copies of the read. Where a base mismatch occurs, the consensus sequence is corrected using majority voting as illustrated in Figure 10. TideHunter [2] was integrated in the genome detective platform to make this possible. The user can customize the minimum required number of repeats before a read is accepted.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of how RCA reads are processed.

First, the repeated fragment is detected in the original long reads with multiple repeats.

The darker regions represent sequencing errors. After decontamination, these errors are eliminated using the majority voting of the other copies.

5.2. Read error correction in Genome Detective

The default assembly algorithm used in Genome Detective reconstructs consensus sequences given all input reads. Because the new wet lab protocol sequences full virus genomes, an assembly step is not required, and only identical sequences should be clustered. This makes it feasible to evaluate the presence of multiple virus variants. A significant number of reads should be identical before they can be considered biological replicates. Algorithms have to consider the circular nature of the begomoviruses when searching for identical copies. In addition, the relatively high error rate of ONT reads makes it

difficult to find completely identical copies. Therefore, new algorithms were implemented to make this possible. First, the circular reads are rotated and linearized so that they follow the numbering of the reference, as illustrated schematically in Figure 11. Secondly, read errors are corrected by comparing information across different reads. The rotated reads are aligned in a multiple sequence's alignment. For every position, the count of every nucleotide is obtained and the algorithm corrects errors by assuming that nucleotide frequencies that are below a minimum threshold are sequencing errors. The threshold is obtained using a binomial distribution, the coverage depth, and the expected error rate for ONT data. This results in much more accurate and identical reads improving the resolution of the dataset.

Figure 11: Alignment of the reads originating from circular template DNA molecules with the starting position of the reference. (A) Unaligned: The grey outer circle represents the reference genome, with two full genome reads having different starting positions. The reads are sequenced in one direction and generate a linear representation of the circular molecule. When reads are unaligned their starting positions do not correspond to the reference. (B) After alignment: The read matches the reference using two local alignments which are written in the alignment BAM File. (C) Alignment after correction: Based on the information from the two partial alignments, the original read is modified (rotated) to match the orientation of the reference genome so that a full genome is represented by a single linear alignment.

5.3. Results

Genome Detective online tool was successfully implemented for analysis of full-length viral genome sequences in Solanaceae (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and Cucurbitaceae (*Cucurbita pepo*) plant samples infected respectively with the begomovirus Tomato yellow leaf curl Sardinia virus (TYLCSV) or the tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) for the solanaceae samples, and with begomovirus Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) for the cucurbitacea samples collected by **KUL** and **CSIC** (D2.3). These results are described in detail in Deliverable 2.3.

After the evaluation, the tool was made available to all members of the consortium and used to examine the diversity of ToLCNDV in naturally infected plants. The analysis of ToLCNDV infected plant samples collected by **INRAE** revealed the presence of complex intraplant ToLCNDV populations (Figure 12). The tool was also proven to resolve mixed infections of closely related ToLCNDV isolates (Figure 13). The output of the analysis will be reported in the D2.5.

Assignment	# Reads	Depth of Coverage	NT Identity	AA Identity	Genome Coverage	Genome Coverage image
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (105 segments out of 2) hide segment info	7475	62.7	80.9%	87.0%	99.9%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	445	444.0	81.2%	86.0%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA A)	387	386.0	90.2%	87.8%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	206	205.0	81.4%	86.7%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	173	172.0	81.3%	86.6%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	165	164.0	81.1%	86.0%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	159	158.0	81.4%	86.9%	100.0%	
Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (segment DNA B)	87	86.0	81.1%	85.9%	100.0%	

Figure 12: Complex intraplant ToLCNDV populations containing multiple virus variants of the ToLCNDV segments A and B in plant sample collected by INRAE.

Figure 13: Mixed infection of closely related ToLCNDV from 3 clades isolates detected in zucchini sample VI231242.1 collected by INRAE.

5.4. Online availability

All improvements are integrated into the online release of Genome Detective Platform since release v2.14.0.

The results are stored in the database and are visualized with the web-based UI.

The RCA processing pipeline can be enabled through a protocol setting which is available for all Virtigation members.

In addition, a protocol setting was added to enable the error correction step to facilitate the analysis of the tobamoviruses.

REFERENCES

1. Vilsker, M., Moosa, Y., Nooij, S., Fonseca, V., Ghysens, Y., Dumon, K., Pauwels, R., Alcantara, L. C., Vanden Eynden, E., Vandamme, A. M., Deforche, K., & de Oliveira, T. (2019). Genome Detective: an automated system for virus identification from high-throughput sequencing data. *Bioinformatics* (Oxford, England), 35(5), 871–873. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty695>
2. Yan Gao, Bo Liu, Yadong Wang, Yi Xing, TideHunter: efficient and sensitive tandem repeat detection from noisy long-reads using seed-and-chain, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 35, Issue 14, July 2019, Pages i200–i207, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz376>